

TARA_	YYYY	MM	DD	PORT (CITY)	LAT	DD	MM.MMM	LONG	DDD	MM.MMM
Start	2022	09	12	Dakar	N	14	40.484	E	017	25.812
End	20yy	09	17	Dakar	N	14	40.484	E	017	25.812

SCIENTIFIC INTEREST & CAMPAING OBJECTIVES

The objectives of the cruise in Casamance river (Senegal) are (i) to observe the changes in microbial life in the river-sea continuum and (ii) to evaluate plastic pollution in the river at its relations with microbes. This work was done in the context of the Microbiome project (2020-2022) that focus on the functional role of the microbial life in the Atlantic and Pacific Oceans.

The research vessel Tara sampled several rivers in South America (including the Amazon) and West Africa during the Microbiome project, providing an opportunity to assess microbiomes and plastics connectivity between rivers and the Atlantic Ocean. Casamance river (Leg18) is the second river sampled totally in Africa (Senegal, September), after the Gambia river (Leg 16) sampled in August, excluding the plume of the Orange river (sampled in June 2022).

PARTICIPANTS

ROLE		NAME, Surname, Affiliation
1	CREW - Captain	Martin Herteau (Tara Ocean Foundation)
2	CREW - 1st Officer	Yves Tournon (Tara Ocean Foundation)
3	CREW - Mecano	Loic Caudan (Tara Ocean Foundation)
4	CREW - Deck	François Aurat (Tara Ocean Foundation)
5	CREW - Deck	David Monmarché (Tara Ocean Foundation)
6	CREW - Cook	Sophie Bin (Tara Ocean Foundation)
7	CREW - Media	Maxime Horlville (Tara Ocean Foundation)
8	GUEST - Artist	Lara Tavet
9	GUEST - Observer	
10	SCIENCE - A - Oceano. Engineer	Josep Maria Herta Montejo (EMS)
11	SCIENCE - B - W-Lab biogeochemistry	Timothée Brochier (IRD)
12	SCIENCE - C - W-Lab genomics	Ange Diehdou (UCAD)
13	SCIENCE - D - S-Lab biogeochemistry	Edouard Lavergne (Plastic@Sea)
14	SCIENCE - E - S-Lab sorting/imaging	Anne-Leila Meistertzheim (Plastic@Sea)
15	SCIENCE - F - additional	Muguette Allegre (IRD)

ENVIRONMENTAL CONTEXT & SAMPLING STRATEGY

Sampling stations are depicted in Figure 1 :

- CAS-01 (station 162-a and 162-b) : it is the reference marine station in front of the Casamance river, but close to the river plume at 10nm of the coastline. It has been sampled at the same location on 2022-09-12 for station 163-a (ebb) and on 2022-09-12 for station 163-b (flow) (Figure 2).
- CAS-02 (station 163-a and 163-b) : it is the estuarine station, close to Nikine beach. It has been sampled at the same location on 2022-09-13 for station 163-a (flow) and for station 163-b (ebb).
- CAS-03 (station 164-a and 164-b) : it is station with intermediate salinity (around 25 in function of the tidal height), close to Brin city. It has been sampled at the same location at anchor on 2022-09-13.
- CAS-04 (station 165) : it is the station with salinity lower than 25, above to Ziguinchor city. It has been sampled on 2022-09-14 with 2 zodiac.
- CAS-05 (station 166) : it is the station with null salinity(freshwater), at Diop Kounda station close to Marandan city. It has been sampled on 2022-09-15 with 4WD.
- Two sampling stations were added under the return travel to Dakar : station 167 : scientific buoy MELAX of IRD researchers) and 168 in front of the Bay of Hann, identified as particularly polluted by macro-plastic litters. These two last stations were sampled only for microplastics (manta 330).

Note : Watershed of the Casamance included 1,5 millions of living people (statistic 2013 with projection to 2020)(Machu et al., in press, European project PADDLE).

Figure 1. Location of sampling stations on the Casamance river (Senegal) during the Leg 18 (13 to September 17, 2022) from the sea (CAS-01_162) to the freshwater (CAS-05_166)

Figure 2. Manta on the Casamance river on the schooner (A) and samplings of the ebb and flow on the estuary station (CAS-02_162)

MAJOR ACHIEVEMENTS

All the work initially planned in Senegal river has been achieved in the Casamance river because of technical limitations (movement of sediments preventing the schooner from entering the river). Because the Ziguinchor bridge did not allowed the research vessel Tara to go further into the river, we used two zodiac to reach the station 165 and 4WD to reach 166 (around 10 miles and 50 miles, respectively, from the Ziguinchor bridge, where we decided to anchor Tara). A clear salinity gradient was known between Nikine and Ziguinchor bridge, and we sampled freshwater in Diop Kounda (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Sampling in freshwater in Diop Kounda close to Marandan city with team on the riverbank and fisherman on the flow.

We have found so many debris in the sampling site on Nikine Beach (station 162) and on the Karabane river bank (station 163) that we stopped sorting the debris (around 20 kg) after only 25m-transect for the OSPAR protocol (instead of the usual 100m transect) (Figure 4). Debris were composed of a lot of clothes, ropes, packaging and fishing nets. The number of packaging litters increased at the Karabane station on the estuary. Interestingly, we found relatively few microplastics when sampling in the river with a manta net.

Figure 4. Collecting (left) and sorting (right) of macro-, meso- and microplastics on the river bank close to Nikine city

However, we found also few microplastics on freshwater. We suggest a preliminary conclusion of high pollution by macroplastic debris localized closed to the cities with few extension to the river, and a relatively low microplastic pollution of the Casamance river. Interestingly, number of microplastics increased in a significant manner closed to the scientific buoy (with a lower salinity, Figure 5) closed to the Senegal river (Dakar) and decreased in front of the Bay of Hann. Further analysis by the partners of the Microbiome project are needed to confirm these observations and to evaluate how much plastic pollution is related to the transport of invasive or pathogen species in the Casamance river and in the Atlantic sea. Relationships between plastic pollution and the dynamic of the environmental parameters along the river-sea continuum (salinity, nutrients, biogeochemistry,...) together with the microbial life in the surrounding waters will also be investigated.

Figure 5. Additional sites for microplastics sampling (A) and cod-end of the manta after 1h of sampling close to the Buoy MELAX (B)

STATION PLAN

Station Title: CAS-01

- **Station Label:** 162-a

Description: Large of the Casamance river close to Nikine city (ebb)

Date: 2022-09-12

Time UTC	Duration	Event	Depth(s)	Comment	A	B	C	D	E
07:00	25 min	Manta 330 net	0-3	SRF horizontal					1
07:40	6 min	WP11 20 net	0-3	SRF horizontal			1	1	
08:35	5 min	WP11 200 net	0-3	SRF horizontal			1	1	
08:16	2 min	Niskin	5	SRF		1	1	1	1

- **Station Label:** 162-b

Description: Large of the Casamance river close to Nikine city (flow)

Date: 2022-09-12

Time UTC	Duration	Event	Depth(s)	Comment	A	B	C	D	E
11:59	60 min	Manta 330 net	0-3	SRF horizontal					1

- **Station Label:** 163-a

Description: Estuary of the Casamance river close to Nikine city (ebb)

Date: 2022-09-13

Time UTC	Duration	Event	Depth(s)	Comment	A	B	C	D	E
07:12	25 min	Manta 330 net	0-3	SRF horizontal					1
07:40	6 min	WP11 20 net	0-3	SRF horizontal			1	1	
08:35	5 min	WP11 200 net	0-3	SRF horizontal			1	1	
09:30	2 min	Niskin	5	SRF		1	1	1	1

- **Station Label:** 163-b

Description: Large of the Casamance river close to Nikine city (flow)

Date: 2022-09-13

Time UTC	Duration	Event	Depth(s)	Comment	A	B	C	D	E
10:52	60 min	Manta 330 net	0-3	SRF horizontal					1

- **Station Label: 164-a**

Description: In the Casamance river close to Brin city

Date: 2022-09-13

Time UTC	Duration	Event	Depth(s)	Comment	A	B	C	D	E
18:40	60 min	Manta 330 net	0-3	SRF horizontal					1
18:21	6 min	WP11 20 net	0-3	SRF horizontal			1	1	
19:54	5 min	WP11 200 net	0-3	SRF horizontal			1	1	
17:54	2 min	Niskin	5	SRF		1	1	1	1

- **Station Label: 165**

Description: In the Casamance river above to Ziguinchor city at intermediate salinity

Date: 2022-09-14

Time UTC	Duration	Event	Depth(s)	Comment	A	B	C	D	E
17:53	40 min	Manta 330 net	0-3	SRF horizontal				1	1
18:20	6 min	WP11 20 net	0-3	SRF horizontal				1	
18:10	5 min	WP11 200 net	0-3	SRF horizontal				1	
18:46	2 min	Niskin	5	SRF		1	1	1	

- **Station Label: 166**

Description: Zero salinity (freshwater) in the Casamance river above Marandan city (no influence of tide), at DiopKounda

Date: 2022-09-15

Time UTC	Duration	Event	Depth(s)	Comment	A	B	C	D	E
11:15	60 min	Manta 330 net	0-3	SRF horizontal				1	1
11:45	2 min	Niskin/Carboy 20L	5	SRF		1	1	1	

- **Station Label: 167**

Description: Between the Casamance and Dakar, at Bouee Melax

Date: 2022-09-17

Time UTC	Duration	Event	Depth(s)	Comment	A	B	C	D	E
08:02	60 min	Manta 330 net	0-3	SRF horizontal				1	1

- **Station Label: 168**

Description: In front of the Bay of Hann with higher plastic pollution o the beach, close to the estuary of Senegal river,

Date: 2022-09-17

Time UTC	Duration	Event	Depth(s)	Comment	A	B	C	D	E
12:56	60 min	Manta 330 net	0-3	SRF horizontal				1	1

OSPAR protocols on beach and river banks

Date	Time UTC	Duration	Event	Comment	A	B	C	D	E
2022-09-12	17:20	85 min	OSPAR	Beach (Nikine)		1	1	1	1
2022-09-13	12:00	60 min	OSPAR	River bank (Karabane hostel)		1	1	1	1

S20-L	5-mL-falcon									4			
PM-HG20	Zip-lock												
MB20	4-mL-Vial									4			
CP50	petri-slide									4			
SCP50	petri-slide												
F200	250-mL-bottle									3			
E200	15-mL-falcon									4			
S200	5-mL-cryotube												4
S200-L	5-mL-falcon									4			
PM-HG200	Zip-lock												
MB200	4-mL-Vial									4			
CP200	petri-slide												
F680	250-mL-bottle												
F2000	250-mL-bottle												
E680	15-mL-falcon												
S680-L	MULTIPLATES												
E2000	15-mL-falcon												
AI	petri-slide	7+2											
AS	2-mL-cryotube												7+2
AF	Zip-lock							7+2					
SP300	2-mL-cryotube												57
MP300	2-mL-cryotube												
CP300	petri-slide												
TOC	30-mL-bottle												
SSML-PC	2-mL-cryotube												
SSML-PT	2-mL-cryotube												
S025-L	15-mL-falcon												
S520-L	5-mL-falcon												
FM5	5-mL-falcon												
TOTAL	256	15		19				45	6	39	12	81	39